

Thermodynamics of 2,2'-Dipyridinium Ion and 1,10-Phenanthroline Ion in *tert*-Butanol-Water and Glycerol-Water Media at 25°

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The enthalpies of formation of the 2,2'-dipyridinium ion and 1, 10-phenanthroline ion in *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water have been determined by calorimetry. Dissociation constants of these ions, in the mixed solvents, have been determined *pH*-metrically. The entropy-changes have been calculated combining the enthalpy values with the corresponding free-energy changes determined from *pK* values. The solubilities of the ligands in pure water and in different *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25° have been determined by spectrophotometry. Hence free energy of transfer of 2,2'-dipyridinium ion and 1, 10-phenanthroline ion from pure water to the different mixed solvent mixtures at 25° have been reported. The role of solvents on the thermodynamic parameters has been discussed.

THERE exists in literature only a few reports on the thermodynamics of the ligands, 2,2'-dipyridyl ("Dipy") and 1,10-phenanthroline ("Ph") in mixed solvents. A number of workers have determined the thermodynamic parameters (ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS°), for the 2,2'-dipyridinium and 1,10-phenanthroline ions in aqueous solution¹⁻⁸. At present there is an increasing interest in the study of the ligands and their complexes in mixed solvents so as to have some idea about the interaction of the solvent. A clear picture is yet to emerge.

In this laboratory we have determined the standard free-energy-changes and enthalpy-changes for different ligands of the type HL(HL \rightarrow H⁺+L⁻) and of the type BH⁺(BH⁺ \rightarrow B+H⁺), iso-electric reaction in aqueo-organic solvents⁹⁻¹². The thermodynamic parameters of iso-electric reaction are of special interest as the reaction is relatively little affected by the change in the dielectric constants of the media.

In order to elucidate further the role of different solvents on the thermodynamic properties as a continuation of our programme, we have determined calorimetrically the enthalpy of formation of PhH⁺ and dipy-H⁺ in different *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25°. *pK* values were determined by *pH*-metry at 25°. Hence free-energy-change, ΔG° , and entropy-change, ΔS° , for the formation of RH⁺ (R stands for Dipy and Ph) in the above mixed solvents were also calculated at this temperature. The solubilities of the neutral base R in pure water and in different *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25° were determined spectrophotometrically. Hence free-energy-change of transfer of Dipy-H⁺ and PhH⁺ from pure water medium to the different mixed solvent mixtures

were calculated using the values of free-energy-change of transfer of H⁺ ions, $\Delta G^\circ_{t(H^+)}$, from aqueous to *t*-BuOH-water mixtures at 25° from literature¹⁴. The values of $\Delta G^\circ_{t(H^+)}$ in glycerol-water mixtures are not available in literature and have been calculated using the Born equation¹⁵ using a value of 9 Å for the radius of H⁺ ion¹⁶.

Experimental

The stock solutions of "Dipy" and "Ph" were prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of the ligand (G.R. - E. Merck) in the desired solvents. Purification of organic solvents have been described in one of our earlier communications¹⁷. Perchloric acid and caustic soda were E. Merck's reagent grade and were estimated in the usual way. All the solutions were made with double-distilled water in an all glass apparatus.

The description of the calorimeter fabricated in our laboratory has been reported earlier¹².

For the measurement of the enthalpy changes of Dipy-H⁺ and PhH⁺ in the mixed solvents, 250 ml of the ligand (strength $\sim 10^{-2}M$) was taken in the Dewar flask and 5 ml of HClO₄ ($\sim 1M$) was taken in the 'Pyrex' glass bulb. This was done to ensure complete conversion of R into RH⁺.

For the determination of *pK* values solutions of very low ionic strength (1×10^{-3} - $6 \times 10^{-4}M$) were used. The *pH* readings were taken with a Cambridge bench-type battery-operated *pH*-meter at 25°.

TABLE 1— pK 's OF $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$ IN AQUEO-ORGANIC MEDIA AT 25°

Wt % of org. component	pK of Dipy- H^+		pK of 1,10-Ph H^+	
	Glycerol-water	<i>t</i> -BuOH-water	Glycerol-water	<i>t</i> -BuOH-water
5	4.40(±0.02)	4.28(±0.02)	4.90(±0.02)	4.76(±0.02)
10	4.32(±0.02)	4.17(±0.02)	4.84(±0.02)	4.64(±0.02)
20	4.16(±0.02)	3.87(±0.02)	4.72(±0.03)	4.28(±0.03)
30	4.04(±0.03)	3.65(±0.02)	4.58(±0.03)	4.04(±0.03)
40	3.96(±0.03)	3.60(±0.03)	4.56(±0.03)	3.96(±0.03)
50	—	3.56(±0.03)	—	3.95(±0.03)

Results and Discussion

From the measured heat liberated, enthalpy change per mole for the reaction: $R + H^+ \rightleftharpoons RH^+$, was calculated using the relation, $\Delta H = -\frac{Q}{x}$, where

Q represents the heat liberated in kJ for x moles of RH^+ formed. The ionic strengths of the solutions in which the reactions have been carried out were ~0.02 to ~0.2M. The reactions are iso-electric in nature. As such the effect of ionic strength was found to be small. The measured ΔH 's were constant within experimental error and therefore have been taken as ΔH^0 's.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant K_T for the equilibrium, $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$ is

$$K_T = \frac{a_R \cdot a_{H^+}}{a_{RH^+}} = \frac{C_R \cdot C_{H^+}}{C_{RH^+}} \frac{f_R f_{H^+}}{f_{RH^+}}$$

has been calculated in the same way as described earlier¹⁰⁻²⁰. The values of pK 's for the Dipy- H^+ and 1,10-Ph H^+ ions are given in Table 1. From the pK 's and ΔH^0 's, $T\Delta S^0$ and ΔG^0 were calculated.

Free energy change of transfer of RH^+ from pure aqueous medium to different mixed solvent media $\Delta G^0_{t(RH^+)}$ were calculated using the following (W→S) relations:

Simplifying the equations as, (1) - (2) + (3) - (4),

$$\Delta G^0_{t(RH^+)} = (x_1 + x_3 - x_2 - x_4) + \Delta G^0_{t(H^+)} \quad (W \rightarrow S)$$

The solubilities and values of $\Delta G^0_{t(RH^+)}$ are given in Tables 2-5.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF Dipy- H^+ FROM WATER TO *t*-BuOH-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°. SOLUBILITY OF Dipy IN WATER = 4.15×10^{-3} (M) $\Delta G^0_{t(H^+)} = 7.89$ kJ mole⁻¹

Wt. % of <i>t</i> -BuOH	Solubility of Dipy (M) × 10	$\Delta G^0_{t(Dipy)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(H^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(Dipy H^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹
10	1.52	4.67	-7.00 (-1.20)*	-8.46 (-2.66)**
20	1.71	4.88	-18.10 (-2.76)	-18.14 (-2.80)
30	2.01	3.98	-18.80 (-4.85)	-12.98 (-4.08)
40	2.83	3.13	-15.20 (-7.76)	-14.98 (-7.54)
50	3.04	2.95	-16.60 (-11.99)	-16.31 (-11.70)

* Values in brackets were calculated using Born equation with $\gamma_{H^+} = 9A^{\circ}(16)$

** Values in brackets were calculated using $\Delta G^0_{H^+}$ values from Born equation.

TABLE 3—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF Dipy- H^+ FROM WATER TO GLYCEROL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

Wt. % of glycerol	Solubility of Dipy (M) × 10 ³	$\Delta G^0_{t(Dipy)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(H^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(Dipy H^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹
10	1.49	10.43	-3.63	3.06
20	2.06	9.62	-7.57	2.77
30	3.62	8.23	-11.98	1.65
40	4.90	7.48	-16.69	0.85

Solubilities of Dipy in water and mixed solvents were determined spectrophotometrically with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. Analytical wave-length = 280 nm, cell-length = 1 cm.

TABLE 4—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF Ph H^+ FROM WATER TO *t*-BuOH-WATER AT 25°

Wt. % of <i>t</i> -BuOH	Solubility of Ph (M) × 10	$\Delta G^0_{t(Ph)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹		
		$\Delta G^0_{t(Ph)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(H^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^0_{t(PhH^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹
10	1.24	5.17	-7.00	-12.83 (-6.58)*
20	1.39	4.89	-13.10	-16.66 (-6.32)
30	1.99	4.00	-13.80	-16.87 (-7.92)
40	2.53	3.41	-15.20	-18.44 (-11.00)
50	2.82	3.14	-16.60	-20.08 (-15.42)

* Values in brackets were calculated using the values of $\Delta G^0_{H^+}$ from Born equation.

TABLE 5—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF PhH^+ FROM WATER TO GLYCEROL-WATER AT 25°

Wt. % of glycerol	Solubility of $\text{Ph}(M) \times 10^3$	$\Delta G^\circ_{\text{Ph}}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\circ_{\text{t}(\text{H}^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\circ_{\text{t}(\text{PhH}^+)}$ kJ mole ⁻¹
10	2.33	9.92	- 3.63	- 2.33
20	2.70	8.95	- 7.57	- 2.43
30	3.05	8.65	- 11.98	- 2.88
40	3.67	8.19	- 16.69	- 3.18

Solubilities of Ph in water and mixed-solvents were determined spectrophotometrically with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. Analytical wave-length = 264 nm, cell-length = 1 cm

The thermodynamic parameters (ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$) for Dipy H^+ in glycerol-water and *t*-BuOH media have been presented in columns 2,3,6,7 10 and 11 in Table 6 and the same for PhH^+ in columns 2,3,6,7, 10 and 11 of Table 7. In columns 4,5,8,9, 12 and 13 of the Tables 6 and 7 the thermodynamic parameters for the same systems in ethanol- and methanol-water (earlier work from this laboratory¹¹⁻¹³) have been incorporated.

Fig. 1 contains a plot of ΔG° against mole fraction of the organic component in the aqueo-organic media for Dipy-H^+ and Fig. 2, a plot of ΔG° against mole-fraction for PhH^+ . In both the cases the plot is linear. For higher percentages it shows some deviations from linearity. The extrapolated values of ΔG° s for pure aqueous medium agree, within experimental errors, with the values directly obtained in water. The values of ΔG° s for PhH^+ and Dipy H^+ in water are 28.87 and 25.48 kJ mole⁻¹ respectively^{11,12}. Similar observations were made in this laboratory for Dipy-H^+ and PhH^+ in ethanol- and methanol-water¹³. It should, however, be borne in mind that the numbers obtained by extrapolation should always be accepted with reservation

 Fig. 1. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$, $-\Delta G^\circ$ and $T\Delta S^\circ$ against mole fraction of organic solvents.

$\text{Dipy} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Dipy H}^+$;
 ○ — *t*-BuOH-Water ; ● — Glycerol-water.

 TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMICS OF THE REACTION, $\text{Dipy-H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Dipy} + \text{H}^+$ AT 25°

Wt. %	ΔG° kJ mole ⁻¹				ΔH° kJ mole ⁻¹				$T\Delta S^\circ$ kJ mole ⁻¹			
	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH
0	25.48	25.48	25.48	25.48	14.23	14.23	12.55	13.60	-11.25	-11.25	-12.93	-11.88
5	25.02	24.35	24.69	25.27	14.48	14.81	14.85	14.56	-10.54	- 9.54	-10.25	-10.71
10	24.60	23.72	24.06	24.81	15.69	16.32	16.74	15.69	- 8.91	- 7.41	- 7.32	- 9.12
20	23.68	22.01	22.72	23.85	18.95	21.00	25.06	20.92	- 4.73	- 1.00	+ 2.34	- 2.93
30	22.97	20.75	21.46	23.01	17.78	22.18	27.20	24.77	- 5.19	+ 1.42	+ 5.73	+ 1.757
40	22.55	20.50	19.71	22.13	16.90	20.00	20.99	21.55	- 5.65	- 0.50	+ 0.59	- 0.59
50	—	20.25	18.83	21.25	16.02	18.74	17.78	18.41	—	- 1.51	- 1.05	- 2.85

 TABLE 7—THERMODYNAMICS FOR THE REACTION, $\text{PhH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Ph} + \text{H}^+$ AT 25°

Wt. %	ΔG° kJ mole ⁻¹				ΔH° kJ mole ⁻¹				$T\Delta S^\circ$ kJ mole ⁻¹			
	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH
0	27.95	27.61	28.83	28.83	16.74	16.74	17.03	17.03	-11.21	-10.88	-11.80	-11.80
5	27.87	27.07	—	28.12	17.49	17.74	—	17.87	-10.38	- 9.93	—	-10.25
10	27.53	26.40	27.70	27.66	18.54	19.00	17.99	20.59	- 9.00	- 7.41	- 9.71	- 7.07
20	26.86	24.35	26.40	26.73	23.56	26.06	19.12	25.02	- 3.31	+ 0.71	- 7.28	- 1.76
30	26.07	22.97	25.02	25.94	22.43	26.53	18.07	19.96	- 3.64	+ 3.56	- 6.95	- 5.98
40	25.94	22.55	—	25.10	20.71	23.99	—	18.20	- 5.23	+ 0.81	—	- 6.90
45	—	—	23.05	24.73	—	—	15.69	17.99	—	—	- 7.36	- 6.74
50	—	22.47	—	24.18	17.74	22.05	—	18.12	—	- 0.42	—	- 6.07
60	—	—	21.09	21.25	—	—	14.43	19.04	—	—	- 6.65	- 2.22

Fig. 2. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$, $-\Delta G^\circ$ and $T\Delta S^\circ$ against mole fraction of organic solvents.
 ○—*t*-BuOH-Water; ●—Glycerol-water.

and wherever possible, a direct determination is desirable.

When one considers the effect of addition of the organic component in water on the dissociation of Dipy H⁺ or PhH⁺ which may be written, in general, as $\text{RH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{R} + \text{H}^+$, it is seen that in both the cases (glycerol- and *t*-BuOH-water systems) ΔG° decreases as the weight percentages of the organic constituent increases. This may be due to increase in the solubility of R in the organic solvent. The greater tendency of R to go into the organic solvent leads to a greater dissociation of RH^+ , which may also be favoured by the difference in the solvational properties of H⁺ and RH^+ . This is substantiated by the fact that the decrease in ΔG° is more in *t*-BuOH-water system compared to that in glycerol-water medium, the solubilities of R being more in *t*-BuOH-water than in glycerol-water (vide

Tables 2-5). Similar decrease in ΔG° has been observed in case of methanol- and ethanol-water media.

The free energy change of transfer, ΔG°_t , from a pure solvent to any other medium for the reaction, $\text{RH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{R} + \text{H}^+$ may be resolved into its individual contributions and written as,

$$\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{dissn})} = \Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)} + \Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{R})} - \Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{RH}^+)}$$

From the solubilities of 'R' $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{R})}$ have been calculated. Taking the value of $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)}$ from literature¹⁴ $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{RH}^+)}$ has been calculated. The last columns in the Tables 2-5 give the values of $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{PhH}^+)}$ or (DipyH^+) in *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water system. Since experimentally determined value $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)}$ in glycerol-water is not available, we have used Born equation for calculating $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)}$ in glycerol. Fig. 3 gives a plot of $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{PhH}^+)}$ against wt % MeOH, *t*-BuOH and $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{DipyH}^+)}$ against wt % *t*-BuOH system in aqueo-organic mixtures. In all these cases one gets a linear plot. The value of $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{PhH}^+)}$ has been calculated from the solubility data by Burgess and Haines²². $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)}$ in methanol-water used is the average value of Tomkins²³ and Alfenaar *et al*²⁴. $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{PhH}^+)}$ and $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{DipyH}^+)}$ in glycerol-water also show linearity but the slope is different. This is possibly due to the fact that $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{neutral})}$ has not been taken into account. It would be interesting to determine experimentally $\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{H}^+)}$ in glycerol-water.

The enthalpy changes for the formation of Dipy-H⁺ and PhH⁺ against mole-fraction of the organic component are represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 3. Plot of $-\Delta G^\circ_{t(\text{RH}^+)}$ against wt. % of organic solvents.
 a—Ref. 23, b—Ref. 24.
 □—Ph H⁺ in *t*-Bu OH; ●—Dipy H⁺ in *t*-BuOH;
 ○—Ph H⁺ in Glycerol; ●—Dipy H⁺ in Glycerol;
 ⊙—Ph H⁺ in MeOH (Av. value of Tomkins²³ & Alfenaar²⁴);
 ▲—Ph H⁺ in MeOH (Tomkins²³).

Figs. 4 and 5 represent the same thermodynamic parameter against weight % of the organic component and $1/D$ (D =dielectric constant of the medium). In view of the low solubility of the substrate "Dipy" and "Ph" it is difficult to determine the enthalpy change by direct calorimetry. So we attempted to get the value of ΔH° in water by the extrapolation of the ΔH° values. The extrapolated values in ΔH° against weight % as well as mole-fraction give the same value within experimental error. For Dipy- H^+ , $\Delta H^\circ = -14.23 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$, which is in agreement with the value reported by Anderegg⁷. The ΔH° value for $PhH^+ = -16.74 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$ which is also in close agreement with the earlier determination from this laboratory²¹.

As seen from the Figs. 1, 2, 4 and 5 the variation of ΔH° with the change in composition of the solvent is not a simple linear variation with solvent composition as in the case of ΔG° s. ΔH° for the process, $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$, is more complex. The curve,

Fig. 4. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$ against wt.% of organic solvents.
○—*t*-BuOH-Water; ●—Glycerol-Water.

Fig. 5. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$ against $1/D$.
○—*t*-BuOH-Water; ●—Glycerol-Water.

in general, passes through a maximum. In case of glycerol-water system the maximum corresponds to 20 wt % of glycerol corresponding to a mole-fraction of 0.04, and in case of *t*-BuOH-water it is 30 wt % corresponding to 0.09 mole fraction of *t*-BuOH.

In the study of the enthalpy of transfer of LiCl and HCl in *t*-BuOH-water medium, Pointud and coworkers²⁵ found that the enthalpy of transfer passes through a maximum at about 27 wt % of *t*-BuOH corresponding to 0.08 mole-fraction of the alcohol.

The heats of solution of different electrolytes in MeOH- and EtOH- H_2O mixtures reported by Mishchenko and coworkers²⁶. Krestov and Klopov²⁷ show that the maxima in the heat of

solution occur at a solvent composition of 0.2 mole-fraction of alcohol.

Figs. 1 and 2 also depict the variation of $T\Delta S^\circ$ with change in the solvent composition. As is seen from the figures, in both the cases $T\Delta S^\circ$ passes through a minimum which indicates that $T\Delta S^\circ$ for the reaction, $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$, passes through a maximum. The maxima in the variation of $T\Delta S^\circ$ against solvent composition are again at the same compositions as observed in the case of variation of ΔH° with solvent composition. Similar observations have been reported earlier in case of ethanol- and methanol-water.

The interpretation of the thermodynamic data in mixed solvent media is difficult as it involves a knowledge of the structure of the liquid mixtures and structure modifications of the media when an ionic system is introduced in the media in addition to ionic solvation effects. It is, however, interesting to compare the thermodynamic properties of a solvent system and see if there be any correlation. For the alcohol-water mixtures the excess free energy of mixing is positive and nearly symmetrical at about $X_2 \approx 0.5$ (X_2 = mole-fraction of alcohol). The excess free energy is comprised of negative and unsymmetrical enthalpy and excess entropy of mixing. For MeOH-water system the minimum in ΔH° is at about $X_2 \approx 0.03$, for EtOH- H_2O , $X_2 \approx 0.02$ and for *t*-BuOH- H_2O at about $X_2 \approx 0.1^{20}$. The minima in $T\Delta S^\circ$ do not occur exactly at the same mole fraction of the organic component. These minima have been interpreted in terms of maximum structuredness of the solvent which the water structure attains by the addition of small amounts of alcohol. Arnett²⁰, however, suggested that in case of ethanol-water system this maximum order is at about $X = 0.1$.

From the correlation of the structural changes of the solvent and the excess thermodynamic properties, logical conclusion would be to interpret the thermodynamic parameters associated with the reaction of the type, $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$, in terms of solubilities, solvational properties of the ligands and the ions and the structuredness of the solvent media based on the concept of Frank and Evans²⁰. Although the reaction is iso-electric, the difference between the sizes of RH^+ and H^+ ions is likely to affect the solvent structure differently. This means a decrease in entropy for the reaction: $RH^+ \rightleftharpoons R + H^+$, because of greater structure making effect of the smaller H^+ ions.

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BANDYOPADHYAY, MANDAL & ADITYA : THERMODYNAMICS OF 2,2'-DIPYRIDINIUM ION ETC.

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